

Extra Keyed Encryption

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June 3, 2026
v 0.2(a)

Abstract

This paper intends to introduce a more powerful form of encryption than a block cipher or any of its previously defined modes of operation. The main goals of a complete symmetric encryption scheme are to provide: encryption, and semantic security; and easily verifiable authentication. Popular modes for encrypting various types of data – such as GCM for interactive data, and XTS for stationary data – introduce specific weaknesses into their encryption or their authentication, which can be fixed with some alterations to already existing encryption and authentication mechanisms.

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1 Introduction

This paper is meant to specify a form of encryption more powerful than the current choices, for the purpose of encrypting interactive data, e.g. internet communication encryption. There are shown weaknesses of previous modes, and this form of encryption is meant to be able to replace them in most uses on moderate hardware. This form is also partially extended to encrypting stationary data, e.g. disk encryption. There are shown weaknesses of common modes for stationary data, and this is meant to be combined with those to increase security by a large margin.

These encryption and authentication functions are made to be based extensively on two functions: block cipher encipherment, and Galois Field operations. Relying on block cipher encipherment and not decipherment allows a moderate speed up when using certain block ciphers, although this is less prevalent in the common AES with the introduction of the AES-NI computer instruction set. Using Galois Field operations will give a considerable speed up if and when dedicated instructions for Galois multiplication or exponentiation are added, although on current hardware, it can be slow if using large Galois Fields.

This paper is not meant as a specification of a mode of operation, it is more: a general template for a strong form of encryption and authentication; and a concept of expanding the Galois / Counter Mode (that these functions are founded on) to allow more functionalities.

In the appendices at the end of the paper, there will be explanations of some concepts that are not usually covered due to being common between most cryptographic releases. There will not be proofs provided for these concepts, only a subset of examples.

2 Conventions

2.1 Formatting Conventions

A number written raw is being represented in base-10 / decimal. A number written as $00111011b$, with an ending b , is being represented in base-2 / binary. A number written as $3Bh$, with an ending h , is being represented in base-16 / hexadecimal. Hexadecimal literals will always use uppercase digits A to and including F.

When a number is written in hexadecimal or binary format, it is written in numeral-wise big-endian format. If written in hexadecimal, it will be assumed to be a multiple of four bits in length, with leading $0h$ characters as needed, as opposed to truncating upper zero bits. When there are several hexadecimal or binary literals stored contiguously, they are written in literal-wise little-endian format. Concatenation is applied by placing the leftmost literal at the lowest place value, and the rightmost literal at the highest place value (with each literal likely taking up a different amount of numerals, based on the literal's own numerals). This means

$$\begin{aligned}
 48h &= (4 \times 16^1) + (8 \times 16^0) \\
 &= 72 \\
 9648h &= (9 \times 16^3) + (6 \times 16^2) + (4 \times 16^1) + (8 \times 16^0) \\
 &= 38472 \\
 96h||48h &\equiv 4896h && (2.1.i) \\
 4896h &= (4 \times 16^3) + (8 \times 16^2) + (9 \times 16^1) + (6 \times 16^0) \\
 &= 18582 \\
 9648h &\not\equiv 96h||48h
 \end{aligned}$$

A bare letter (a, B, γ) stores a function or a piece of information, such as a length or an index. A letter with a dot ($\dot{a}, \dot{B}, \dot{\gamma}$) stores a single bit of data. A letter with a hat ($\hat{a}, \hat{B}, \hat{\gamma}$) stores a single block-cipher sized block of data (a small block / sblock). A letter with a bar ($\bar{a}, \bar{B}, \bar{\gamma}$) stores a 32-bit word. A letter with two dots ($\ddot{a}, \ddot{B}, \ddot{\gamma}$) stores a binary row vector, in big-endian format, the length of an sblock in bits. A letter with three dots ($\dddot{a}, \dddot{B}, \dddot{\gamma}$) represents a binary square matrix, the width of an sblock in bits and the length of an sblock in bits. A boldened form of any of these ($\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{\gamma}$) stores an array / string of that datatype, rather than a single one, where an array / string length can be any non-negative integer. Using the same letter does not mean the two datapieces are related if they are different datatypes, though they often will be related at the least.

When indexing arrays, indices start from 0, which means the element of an array with no elements before it is at index 0, not index 1. To index an array, one of the two following methods will be used: if $\hat{\mathbf{A}}[0 : 16]$ is used, then the range of blocks, starting at block 0, up to but not including block 16 (which means 16 blocks in total), will be treated as one large operand, for example when filling one array with data from another array; if $\hat{\mathbf{A}}[0 \leq i < 16]$ is used, then the range is the same, but the block index is stored in i , and the line of the equation will essentially be repeated for every possible index of i within the range. Additionally, a range can be given by, for example, $[31 : 15 : -1]$, where the blocks added in reverse order (due to the third value being -1 , which means the next block index I_{i+1} is $I_i - 1$), and now it includes 31 and excludes 15.

2.2 Definitions, Variables, and Functions

α	An arbitrary generator element of the primary field in use
$\dot{\mathbf{A}}$	The bit string of public authentication data
\mathbb{b}	\mathbb{Z}_2 , the set of bit values, $\{0, 1\}$
\mathbb{b}^*	The set of bit strings of any length
$\dot{\mathbf{C}}$	The bit string of ciphertext
$\hat{\mathbf{C}}$	The sblock string of ciphertext
	Ciphertext type returned will be shown in the equations for the function of the encryption scheme and so will always be specified
$d(\dot{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{C}})$	The decryption function of the underlying block cipher
$e(\dot{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{P})$	The encryption function of the underlying block cipher
η	A number related to a bit string's length
$\text{gcd}(a, b, \dots)$	The greatest common divisor / highest common factor of a , b , etc, i.e. the largest number that divides all inputs with remainder 0
$\text{GF}(2)$	\mathbb{Z}_2 , the set of integers mod 2, $\{0, 1\}$

$\mathbb{GF}(2^8)$ The polynomial ring over $\mathbb{GF}(2)$ with a degree 8 modulus polynomial, specifically

$$\mathbb{Z}_2[x]/(x^8 \oplus x^4 \oplus x^3 \oplus x \oplus 1)$$

$\mathbb{GF}(2^{127})$ The polynomial ring over $\mathbb{GF}(2)$ with a degree 127 modulus polynomial, specifically

$$\mathbb{Z}_2[x]/(x^{127} \oplus x \oplus 1)$$

$\mathbb{GF}(2^{128})$ The polynomial ring over $\mathbb{GF}(2)$ with a degree 128 modulus polynomial, specifically

$$\mathbb{Z}_2[x]/(x^{128} \oplus x^7 \oplus x^2 \oplus x \oplus 1)$$

$\mathbb{GF}(2^{256})$ The polynomial ring over $\mathbb{GF}(2)$ with a degree 256 modulus polynomial, specifically

$$\mathbb{Z}_2[x]/(x^{256} \oplus x^{10} \oplus x^5 \oplus x^2 \oplus 1)$$

$\mathbb{GF}(2^{512})$ The polynomial ring over $\mathbb{GF}(2)$ with a degree 512 modulus polynomial, specifically

$$\mathbb{Z}_2[x]/(x^{512} \oplus x^8 \oplus x^5 \oplus x^2 \oplus 1)$$

$\mathbb{GF}(2^{521})$ The polynomial ring over $\mathbb{GF}(2)$ with a degree 521 modulus polynomial, specifically

$$\mathbb{Z}_2[x]/(x^{521} \oplus x^{32} \oplus 1)$$

$\mathbb{GF}(2^{1024})$ The polynomial ring over $\mathbb{GF}(2)$ with a degree 1024 modulus polynomial, specifically

$$\mathbb{Z}_2[x]/(x^{1024} \oplus x^5 \oplus x^3 \oplus x \oplus 1)$$

information	A datatype consisting of ‘real-world’ values, such as true, false, integers, and occasionally floating-points / ‘reals’
$\dot{\mathbf{I}}$	The bit string of the initialisation vector
$\dot{\mathbf{K}}$	The bit string of the primary key
ℓ	The bit length of a single block of the underlying block cipher, for some pieces of evidence it is required that $\ell \in \{2^x : 1 < x \in \mathbb{Z}\}$, this will be implicit until the ending notes
λ	The sblock length of a single lblock
λ_i	The ceiling of the logarithm of λ base 2
lblock	A large block, an element of $\mathbb{S}^\lambda \cong \mathbb{b}^{\ell \times \lambda}$
$\mathbb{M}(2^\ell)$	The matrix space equivalent of $\mathbb{GF}(2^\ell)^\ell$, $\mathbb{Z}_2^{\ell \times \ell}$, represented as ℓ columns of transposed vectors, vectors \ddot{v}_i^\top where $\ddot{v}_i \in \mathbb{V}(2^\ell)$
$\mathbb{M}_H(2^\ell)$	The homogenous extension of matrix space $\mathbb{M}(2^\ell)$, i.e. $\mathbb{Z}_2^{(\ell+1) \times (\ell+1)}$
$\min_{i \geq 0}(f(i))$	The lowest integer value of $i \geq 0$ such that $f(i)$ evaluates to true
n	The amount of keys in use for TnEKE
$\omega(\hat{\zeta})$	A function that returns the multiplicative order of the element supplied in the primary field
$\dot{\mathbf{P}}$	The bit string of plaintext
$\hat{\mathbf{P}}$	The sblock string of plaintext
$\pi_\eta(\dot{\mathbf{M}})$	Plaintext type taken will be shown in the equations for the given function, and so will always be specified The padding function that appends an amount of 0 bits in the range $\{0, 1, \dots, \eta - 2, \eta - 1\}$ to the message given to make the total amount of bits returned a multiple of η ; alternatively, really any padding scheme that pads to η -bit blocks and retains the message (with or without length retention, since length is anyway authenticated), where η is only ℓ or $\ell \times \lambda$

$\phi_\eta(\dot{\mathbf{M}})$	The length function that returns the amount of η -bit blocks in the message, regardless of string type, $\phi_\eta(\dot{\mathbf{M}}) = \lceil \frac{ \dot{\mathbf{M}} \times 1}{\eta} \rceil$, $\phi_\eta(\hat{\mathbf{M}}) = \lceil \frac{ \hat{\mathbf{M}} \times \ell}{\eta} \rceil$, etc
$\phi_\eta(n)$	The ceiling function, $\lceil \frac{n}{\eta} \rceil$
$\dot{\mathbf{S}}$	The bit string of extra keying data
\mathbb{S}	The set of sblocks, the set of integers mod 2^ℓ
\mathbb{S}^*	The set of sblock strings of any length
sblock	A small block, an element of \mathbb{S}
$\dot{\mathbf{T}}$	The (predictable) tweak in use for a single lblock of TnEKE
τ	The length of the requested authentication tag in bits
$\mathbb{V}(2^\ell)$	The row vector space equivalent of $\mathbb{GF}(2^\ell)$, \mathbb{Z}_2^ℓ , with the lowest bit (values 1, 1) on the right and the highest bit (values $2^{\ell-1}$, $x^{\ell-1}$) on the left (i.e. big-endian)
$\mathbb{V}_H(2^\ell)$	The homogenous extension of vector space $\mathbb{V}(2^\ell)$, i.e. $\mathbb{Z}_2^\ell \times \{1\}$
$\dot{\mathbf{Y}}$	The authentication tag bit string
$\mathbb{Z}/(2^{130} - 5)$	The field of integers mod $2^{130} - 5$, specifically for Poly1305
ζ	An arbitrary element of the primary field

2.3 Operators

$\hat{\mathbf{A}} := \hat{\mathbf{B}}$	Setting one variable to a value when the datatypes are the same
$\hat{\mathbf{A}} \stackrel{e}{\leftarrow} \dot{\mathbf{B}}[0 : \ell]$	Setting an sblock to the right operand, transformed into an sblock, then encrypted; the line on the left is equivalent to $\hat{\mathbf{A}} := e(\dot{\mathbf{K}}, \dot{\mathbf{B}}[0 : \ell] \rightarrow \mathbb{S})$
$\hat{\mathbf{A}} \stackrel{e, \dot{\mathbf{K}}_i}{\leftarrow} \dot{\mathbf{B}}[0 : \ell]$	$\hat{\mathbf{A}} \stackrel{e}{\leftarrow} \dot{\mathbf{B}}[0 : \ell]$ with specified encipherment key $\dot{\mathbf{K}}_i$

$\hat{A} \leftarrow \hat{B}$	Setting a variable to a value after a type conversion, when the datatypes are different; all conversions will be done in complete little-endian, where the lowest place value of the larger item is equivalent to the first item of the smaller item
$\hat{A} \rightarrow \mathbb{b}^*$	In place type conversion from one type to another type; same application as \leftarrow
$\hat{A} == \hat{B}$	A bit or piece of information depending on context, 1 if the two operands are the same type, and every part of them is the same value (including length if strings), and 0 otherwise
$a \ll b$	Indicates the right operand is much larger than the left operand
$\hat{A} \ll_s b$	The left operand shifted left (shift direction is based on big-endian ‘left’) by the right operand as a bit count, $(bits_b : 0) \ll \hat{A}$
$\hat{A} \ll_R b$	The left operand rotated left (rotation direction is based on big-endian ‘left’) by the right operand as a bit count, $(bits_{ \hat{A} } : (\hat{A} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}) \times 2^b) \oplus (bits_{ \hat{A} } : \lfloor (\hat{A} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}) * 2^{b- \hat{A} } \rfloor)$
$ \hat{A} $	Length, in primitive sizes of the operand, meaning if the operand is a bit string it is in bits, if the operand is an sblock string it is in sblocks
$(bits_\eta : \hat{A})$	Returns the lowest η bits of the operand, where the operand can be information or a block, or a longer bit string, and the operand is a bit string
$a * b$	Real multiplication
$a \div b$	Real division
$\frac{a}{b}$	Real division
$a + b$	Integer addition
$\sum_{i=a}^{b-1} (f(i))$	Integer sum
$a \times b$	Integer multiplication
$\prod_{i=a}^{b-1} (f(i))$	Integer product
a^n	Integer exponentiation
$\hat{A} \oplus \hat{B}$	Galois / xor addition

$\bigoplus_{i=a}^{b-1}(f(i))$	Galois / xor sum
$\hat{A} \otimes \hat{B}$	Galois multiplication
$\bigotimes_{i=a}^{b-a}(f(i))$	Galois product
\hat{A}^n	Galois exponentiation
$\ddot{a} \odot \ddot{b}^\top$	Binary vector dot product
$\ddot{a} \odot \ddot{b}$	Binary vector-matrix dot product
\ddot{a}^\top	Column vector representation of \ddot{a}
\ddot{a}^\top	Transposed view of \ddot{a}

3 Precursor Systems

3.1 Electronic Codebook Mode

Electronic Codebook Mode (ECB) is a mode that takes a plaintext padded to the sblock length and individually encrypts each block. It is parallelisable, and provides no semantic security other than within a single block.

$$\hat{\mathbf{C}}[0 \leq i < |\hat{\mathbf{P}}|] := e(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{P}}[i]) \quad (3.1.i)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{P}}[0 \leq i < |\hat{\mathbf{C}}|] := d(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{C}}[i]) \quad (3.1.ii)$$

[Equation 3.1.i](#) shows the encryption flow, and [Equation 3.1.ii](#) shows the decryption flow.

3.2 Galois / Counter Mode

The primary field for this section is $\mathbb{GF}(2^{128})$.

Galois / Counter Mode (GCM) [[McgVie05^a](#)] [[Dwo07^a](#)] is an AEAD mode, meaning Authenticated Encryption with Additional Data, which means there are two data streams, one to be encrypted, one to be passed straight through on the connection, but both are authenticated together. It works by first carrying out Counter Mode (CTR) encryption, where a unique predictable block is enciphered to form a unique high-entropy block, which is then xored with the corresponding plaintext block to form the corresponding ciphertext block. Due to being a stream cipher, this encryption can take partial final blocks, and is also incredibly malleable. The next part of the function uses the Galois Message Authentication Code (GMAC), which is the authentication of the ciphertext and additional data. It constructs a polynomial over a 128-bit Galois Field, using the lengths of the data streams, as well as the ciphertext and additional data, with a pseudorandom key-nonce-based constant term, and then evaluates it at a key dependent x-value in order to compress it. This means, in addition to being powerful, it is also random access on decryption, after verification of the ciphertext (which does not require decryption anyway, and can be done in any order of blocks as long as the true location of a block is known).

$$\ell = 128$$

$$\lambda = \text{none}$$

$$\tau = 128$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{\xi} &:= e(\dot{\mathbf{K}}, (\text{bits}_{128} : 0) \rightarrow \mathbb{S}) \\
&\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \hat{\iota} \leftarrow (\text{bits}_{32} : 1) \parallel \dot{\mathbf{I}} \\ \left[\begin{array}{l} \hat{\mathbf{i}} \leftarrow \pi_{128}(\dot{\mathbf{I}}) \parallel (\text{bits}_{64} : 0) \parallel (\text{bits}_{64} : |\dot{\mathbf{I}}|) \\ \hat{\iota} := \bigoplus_{j=0}^{|\hat{\mathbf{i}}|-1} (\hat{\mathbf{i}}[j] \otimes \hat{\xi}^{(|\hat{\mathbf{i}}|-j)}) \end{array} \right] \end{array} \right. \begin{array}{l} \text{if } |\dot{\mathbf{I}}| = 96 \\ \text{if } |\dot{\mathbf{I}}| \neq 96 \end{array} \\
\hat{\mathbf{Q}}[0 \leq i < \phi_{128}(\dot{\mathbf{P}})] &\leftarrow (\text{bits}_{128} : \hat{\iota}) - (\text{bits}_{32} : \hat{\iota}) + (\text{bits}_{32} : \hat{\iota} + i + 1) \\
\hat{\mathbf{Q}}[0 \leq i < \phi_{128}(\dot{\mathbf{P}})] &:= e(\dot{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\mathbf{Q}}[i]) \\
\dot{\mathbf{C}}[0 : |\dot{\mathbf{P}}|] &:= \dot{\mathbf{P}} \oplus (\dot{\mathbf{Q}} \rightarrow \mathbb{b}^*)[0 : |\dot{\mathbf{P}}|] \\
\hat{\mathbf{U}} &:= e(\dot{\mathbf{K}}, \hat{\iota}) \\
\hat{\mathbf{V}} &\leftarrow \pi_{128}(\dot{\mathbf{A}}) \parallel \pi_{128}(\dot{\mathbf{C}}) \parallel (\text{bits}_{64} : |\dot{\mathbf{A}}|) \parallel (\text{bits}_{64} : |\dot{\mathbf{C}}|) \\
\hat{\mathbf{Y}} &:= \bigoplus_{j=0}^{|\hat{\mathbf{V}}|-1} (\hat{\mathbf{V}}[j] \otimes \hat{\xi}^{(|\hat{\mathbf{V}}|-j)}) \\
\dot{\mathbf{Y}} &\leftarrow \hat{\mathbf{Y}} \oplus \hat{\mathbf{U}}
\end{aligned} \tag{3.2.i}$$

Equation 3.2.i shows: the creation of $\hat{\xi}$, the x-value; the encryption of $\dot{\mathbf{P}}$, the plaintext, into $\dot{\mathbf{C}}$, the ciphertext; and the authentication of $\dot{\mathbf{A}}$, the additional data, and $\dot{\mathbf{C}}$ into $\dot{\mathbf{Y}}$, the authentication tag. Note that this will produce different results to the standardised GCM functionality, but is equally strong, and mostly similar in function (see Section A.1, Item 1). Additionally, the reason for the “backwards” polynomial evaluation is that it allows efficient processing of the polynomial evaluation without reducing security. This is because it allows forward processing, where each data block is processed after the one before it in memory, as opposed to after the one preceding it in memory, by using Horner’s method, in which the current y-value (the initial y-value is 0) is added to the next coefficient, then multiplied by the x-value, in order to form the next y-value, with the last y-value being the finalised and correct y-value. GCM is only standardised for 128-bit block ciphers, and so ℓ is fixed at 128. There is no sense of lblocks in GCM, and so λ is set to none (not 0, but not a value, as it is worthless). One block’s worth of authentication is produced as a tag, and so τ is fixed at $1 \times \ell = 128$.

This has a flaw, as the x-value used does not undergo any kind of sampling, and GCM does not allow repeated authentication of an additional data and ciphertext pair. This means, if the selected x-value is not a multiplicative generator, it could be that not all of the coefficients in the authentication polynomial are used. For example, the polynomial evaluation for authenti-

cation can be rearranged to show

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{Y} := & (\hat{\mathbf{V}}[0] \otimes \hat{\xi}^{(|\hat{\mathbf{V}}|-0)}) \oplus (\hat{\mathbf{V}}[3] \otimes \hat{\xi}^{(|\hat{\mathbf{V}}|-3)}) \oplus \dots \\ & \oplus (\hat{\mathbf{V}}[1] \otimes \hat{\xi}^{(|\hat{\mathbf{V}}|-1)}) \oplus (\hat{\mathbf{V}}[4] \otimes \hat{\xi}^{(|\hat{\mathbf{V}}|-4)}) \oplus \dots \\ & \oplus (\hat{\mathbf{V}}[2] \otimes \hat{\xi}^{(|\hat{\mathbf{V}}|-2)}) \oplus (\hat{\mathbf{V}}[5] \otimes \hat{\xi}^{(|\hat{\mathbf{V}}|-5)}) \oplus \dots \end{aligned} \quad (3.2.ii)$$

and if the multiplicative order of $\hat{\xi}$ is 3, meaning $\hat{\xi}^3 = 1$, then this can be simplified to

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{Y} := & (\hat{\mathbf{V}}[0] \oplus \hat{\mathbf{V}}[3] \oplus \dots) \otimes \hat{\xi}^{(|\hat{\mathbf{V}}|-0)} \\ & \oplus (\hat{\mathbf{V}}[1] \oplus \hat{\mathbf{V}}[4] \oplus \dots) \otimes \hat{\xi}^{(|\hat{\mathbf{V}}|-1)} \\ & \oplus (\hat{\mathbf{V}}[2] \oplus \hat{\mathbf{V}}[6] \oplus \dots) \otimes \hat{\xi}^{(|\hat{\mathbf{V}}|-2)} \end{aligned} \quad (3.2.iii)$$

which means, generally, if the order of $\hat{\xi}$, shown here as $\omega(\hat{\xi})$, is less than $2^{128} - 1$ (which means it is a factor by construction), then blocks $\hat{\mathbf{V}}[i]$ and $\hat{\mathbf{V}}[i + k \times \omega(\hat{\xi})]$ are never used on their own, but together as $\hat{\mathbf{V}}[i] \oplus \hat{\mathbf{V}}[i + k \times \omega(\hat{\xi})]$. Technically, this is still applicable when $\omega(\hat{\xi}) = 2^{128} - 1$, but that requires such a large polynomial (even some common $\omega(\hat{\xi}) < 2^{128} - 1$ require an infeasibly large polynomial to use) that it is a useless attack.

Despite this, it can still be useful to quantify the utility of this weakness. We can begin by finding this weakness in a toy field, such as $\ell = 8$, using $\mathbb{GF}(2^8)$, which has 256 elements, 255 of which are in its multiplicative group. The order of an element, $\hat{\zeta} > 0$, will be defined as the smallest integer $\Omega > 0$ such that $\hat{\zeta}^\Omega = 1$ in the field. This will be defined as $\Omega = \omega(\hat{\zeta})$. This can be described as below.

$$\begin{aligned} \omega(\hat{\zeta}) & \geq 1 - (\hat{\zeta} == 0) \\ \omega(\hat{\zeta}) & < 2^\ell \\ \omega(0) & = 0 \\ \omega(\hat{\alpha}) & = 2^\ell - 1 \\ \omega(\hat{\zeta} \neq 0) & = \min_{n>0} (\hat{\zeta}^n = 1) \end{aligned} \quad (3.2.iv)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \omega(\hat{\alpha}^k) & = \frac{2^\ell - 1}{\gcd(2^\ell - 1, k)} \\ \omega(\hat{\zeta}^k) & = \frac{\omega(\hat{\zeta})}{\gcd(\omega(\hat{\zeta}), k)} \end{aligned}$$

However, in the tables, the order of the element 0 will be counted as 1, due to reasons explained later. We can then count groups of elements by their order, resulting in the table below. On the left is the order in elements, Ω , as well as the order as a part of the order of a generator, $\Omega/(2^\ell - 1)$. On the right is the count of elements with that order, n , as well as the density of these elements, $n/(2^\ell)$.

order 1 or "0" relative 3.9216×10^{-3}	count 2 density 7.8125×10^{-3}
order 3 relative 1.1765×10^{-2}	count 2 density 7.8125×10^{-3}
order 5 relative 1.9608×10^{-2}	count 4 density 1.5625×10^{-2}
order 15 relative 5.8824×10^{-2}	count 8 density 3.1250×10^{-2}
order 17 relative 6.6667×10^{-2}	count 16 density 6.2500×10^{-2}
order 51 relative 2.0000×10^{-1}	count 32 density 1.2500×10^{-1}
order 85 relative 3.3333×10^{-1}	count 64 density 2.5000×10^{-1}
order 255 relative 1.0000×10^0	count 128 density 5.0000×10^{-1}

Table 1: $\mathbb{GF}(2^8)$ order table

This gives us a pattern, in that each prime Ω contains $\Omega - 1$ elements (since it is an Ω sized loop that includes the element 1, which is only counted as $\omega(1) = 1$), and the other orders, $\Omega_2 = \Omega_0 \times \Omega_1$, contain $n_2 = n_0 \times n_1$ elements. Again, this is calculated when $\omega(0) = 0$, and after calculating all rows of the table, $\omega(0)$ is then displayed as 1, for purposes shown later. This can then be trivially expanded to other Galois Fields, such as $\mathbb{GF}(2^{128})$, but factors $2^{32} + 1$ and $2^{64} + 1$ can be factored further ($2^{32} + 1 = 641 \times 6700417$, $2^{64} + 1 = 274177 \times 67280421310721$). This means there are 9 prime factors of $2^{128} - 1$, and so 512 factors in total, i.e. 512 rows in a table of this style. This is too large to show, but can still be calculated easily. The prime table will be displayed here.

order 3 relative 8.8162×10^{-39}	count 2 density 5.8775×10^{-39}
order 5 relative 1.4694×10^{-38}	count 4 density 1.1755×10^{-38}
order 17 relative 4.9959×10^{-38}	count 16 density 4.7020×10^{-38}
order 257 relative 7.5526×10^{-37}	count 256 density 7.5232×10^{-37}
order 641 relative 1.8837×10^{-36}	count 640 density 1.8808×10^{-36}
order 65537 relative 1.9260×10^{-34}	count 65536 density 1.9259×10^{-34}
order 274177 relative 8.0573×10^{-34}	count 274176 density 8.0573×10^{-34}
order 6700417 relative 1.9691×10^{-32}	count 6700416 density 1.9691×10^{-32}
order 67280421310721 relative 1.9772×10^{-25}	count 67280421310720 density 1.9772×10^{-25}

Table 2: $\mathbb{GF}(2^{128})$ prime order table

If we complete the table, with all 512 entries, we see that the average relative order of an element is roughly 0.6138012825 [Sin26^a]. This means the average amount of affective blocks in the polynomial is $(2^{128} - 1) \times 0.6138012825 = 2.0887 \times 10^{38}$. The reason that $\omega(0)$ is reset to be 1 after calculating all of the other rows is that the measure we use is affective coefficients. If we compare the two 1-order items, $\hat{\xi} = 1$ would mean every coefficient is xored together to create the tag. If we have $\hat{\xi} = 0$, only the first coefficient of the polynomial creates the tag. While they act very differently under chosen plaintext attacks and above, they both have a single affective block, i.e. only use one power of the x-value, and so neither of them are really polynomial evaluations.

A $\hat{\xi}$ such that $\omega(\hat{\xi}) < 2^\ell - 1$ naturally lends itself to an authentication attack that can remove existential unforgeability:

1. We assume a CMA-like environment, with an extra verification oracle. The nonce for encryption and verification is controlled to an extent: the encryption oracle selects a random nonce, gives a ciphertext and tag, as well as a ‘handle’ type object with which the nonce used for the encryption can be referenced (e.g. a simple “nonce n^o1”) without revealing what the nonce is to the attacker or letting the attacker di-

rectly control it, and the verification oracle can be given each nonce handle once, and will perform verification with the referenced nonce. This environment is reminiscent of a third party potentially altering ciphertexts and tags, sending them to the intended receiver, and listening for a decryption failure (without obtaining the plaintext on a success).

2. Recall that

$$\begin{aligned}\omega(\hat{\alpha}) &= 2^\ell - 1 \\ \omega(\hat{\alpha}^k) &= \frac{\omega(\hat{\alpha})}{\gcd(\omega(\hat{\alpha}), k)} \\ &= \frac{2^\ell - 1}{\gcd(2^\ell - 1, k)}\end{aligned}$$

and that $\hat{\alpha}^k$ can describe any element $\hat{\zeta} \neq 0$, since $\hat{\alpha}$ is a multiplicative generator.

3. Recall that $2^{128} - 1$ has nine prime factors, and thus 512 divisors.

4. Use 9 or 10 chosen plaintexts and 9 or 10 chosen ciphertext-tag verifications (the amount of times it requires 10 is negligible) to find $\omega(\hat{\xi})$.

(a) Select n , a prime factor of $2^{128} - 1$ (it is more feasible to produce in realistic terms if n is first selected to be the largest prime factor, and decreased as the tests continue).

(b) Find $n' = \frac{2^{128}-1}{n}$

(c) Test if n is a factor of $\omega(\hat{\xi})$ by submitting the ciphertext returned from a chosen plaintext query into the verification oracle, but with $\hat{\mathbf{C}}[i]$ and $\hat{\mathbf{C}}[i + n']$ swapped (and with the same authentication tag). If it succeeds, then n is not a factor of $\omega(\hat{\xi})$. If it fails, n is a factor of $\omega(\hat{\xi})$.

(d) Continue for the remaining 8 selections of n .

- If a prime factor of $2^{128} - 1$, n_1 , is found to not be a factor of $\omega(\hat{\xi})$, then on further tests for a factor of $2^{128} - 1$, n_2 , n'_2 can be defined as $\frac{2^{128}-1}{n_1 \times n_2}$ instead of $\frac{2^{128}-1}{n_2}$, which allows for potentially shorter plaintexts required. This is why the largest n is selected for the first tests, it is a relatively low possibility, but if successful, it can make all tests much easier. (If neither n_1 nor n_2 are factors of $\omega(\hat{\xi})$, then n'_3 can be calculated as $\frac{2^{128}-1}{n_1 \times n_2 \times n_3}$. Essentially, all prime non-factors from previous

tests should be used in each subsequent test to make queries to oracles as short as possible.)

- The scenario in which 10 chosen ciphertexts are needed is when $\omega(\hat{\xi}) = 1$, as we know $\hat{\xi} = 0, 1$. These specific scenarios can be useful to distinguish due to specific properties, and so a further test with an arbitrary block garbled (such as a single bit flip, with no corresponding bit flip in another block) will indicate $\hat{\xi} = 0$ on success, and indicate $\hat{\xi} = 1$ on failure.
 - Many methods can be used to maul $\hat{C}[i]$ and $\hat{C}[i + n']$, and will give the same result provided $\hat{C}[i] \oplus \hat{C}[i + n'] = \hat{C}'[i] \oplus \hat{C}'[i + n']$ (where \hat{C}' is \hat{C} after the mauling). Swapping is just a simple one.
5. Calculate $\Omega = \omega(\hat{\xi})$ exactly, using its divisibility by each of the prime factors of $2^{128} - 1$, and also the 0-test (requiring the extra 1 encryption and 1 verification queries) if none were factors.
 6. Create another chosen plaintext query, with a plaintext length of at least $\Omega + 1$ blocks, and alter the returned ciphertext like before, using Ω instead of n .
 7. This altered ciphertext, with the very same authentication tag returned by the encryption oracle, should be successfully verified by the verification oracle.

This attack has a slightly less than 0.5 chance to fail to reduce it beyond the trivial $\omega(\hat{\xi}) = 2^\ell - 1$ for $\ell \in \{2^x : 1 < x \in \mathbb{Z}\}$. Like before, the average ratio it will be reduced to is roughly 0.6138012825, and so will require, on average, a 2.0887×10^{38} sblock fake plaintext, or 1.2276×2^{134} bits. The median plaintext size required is 1.3333×2^{133} bits, which is a third of the bits required to break a maximum strength tag.

3.3 ChaCha20-Poly1305

The primary field for this section is $\mathbb{Z}/(2^{130} - 5)$

ChaCha20-Poly1305 [NirLan^a] is an encryption and authentication combined mechanism. ChaCha20 is a stream cipher similar to Counter Mode (CTR) of a block cipher, except ChaCha20 works by combining a key, a nonce, and a position code into a block, and then using an algorithm similar to a hash function, where the block is pseudorandomly permuted (with no key changing the permutation, the only key is in the block) into another block, which is then xored with the original block to remove feasible preimaging.

The block [NirLan15,1^b] is a 512-bit value, represented as a 4x4 square of 32-bit values. The permutation is based off of a ‘quarter round’, which is a permutation of 4 32-bit words, and this quarter round is, in each round, repeated four times. A pair of rounds is called a ‘double round’, and if we index the rounds from 0, then even round numbers mix words within a column, and odd round numbers mix words within a south-east diagonal.

The quarter round is defined as a function $(\bar{y}_0, \bar{y}_1, \bar{y}_2, \bar{y}_3) = Q(\bar{x}_0, \bar{x}_1, \bar{x}_2, \bar{x}_3)$.

$$\begin{aligned}
(\bar{y}_0, \bar{y}_1, \bar{y}_2, \bar{y}_3) &:= (\bar{x}_0, \bar{x}_1, \bar{x}_2, \bar{x}_3) \\
\bar{y}_0 &:= (\text{bits}_{32} : \bar{y}_0 + \bar{y}_1) \\
\bar{y}_3 &:= (\bar{y}_0 \oplus \bar{y}_3) \ll_R 16 \\
\bar{y}_2 &:= (\text{bits}_{32} : \bar{y}_2 + \bar{y}_3) \\
\bar{y}_1 &:= (\bar{y}_1 \oplus \bar{y}_2) \ll_R 12 \\
\bar{y}_0 &:= (\text{bits}_{32} : \bar{y}_0 + \bar{y}_1) \\
\bar{y}_3 &:= (\bar{y}_0 \oplus \bar{y}_3) \ll_R 8 \\
\bar{y}_2 &:= (\text{bits}_{32} : \bar{y}_2 + \bar{y}_3) \\
\bar{y}_1 &:= (\bar{y}_1 \oplus \bar{y}_2) \ll_R 7
\end{aligned} \tag{3.3.i}$$

The state can be shown like this, where each value is a single 32-bit word:

$\bar{x}_{0,0}$	$\bar{x}_{1,0}$	$\bar{x}_{2,0}$	$\bar{x}_{3,0}$
$\bar{x}_{0,1}$	$\bar{x}_{1,1}$	$\bar{x}_{2,1}$	$\bar{x}_{3,1}$
$\bar{x}_{0,2}$	$\bar{x}_{1,2}$	$\bar{x}_{2,2}$	$\bar{x}_{3,2}$
$\bar{x}_{0,3}$	$\bar{x}_{1,3}$	$\bar{x}_{2,3}$	$\bar{x}_{3,3}$

The full ChaCha20 function consists of 20 rounds, or 10 double rounds, followed by an addition with the input block, to compute a preimage resistant pseudorandom block. The input will be $\bar{x}_{0 \leq i < 4, 0 \leq j < 4}$, and the output will be $\bar{y}_{0 \leq i < 4, 0 \leq j < 4}$. Also assume subtext for \bar{y} is mod 4, so $\bar{y}_{(3,9)} = \bar{y}_{(3,1)}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\bar{y}_{(0 \leq i < 4, 0 \leq j < 4)} &:= \bar{x}_{(i,j)} \\
&\text{forall } (0 \leq r < 10) \text{ do } \{ \\
&\text{forall } (0 \leq i < 4) \text{ do } \{ \\
(\bar{y}_{(i,0)}, \bar{y}_{(i,1)}, \bar{y}_{(i,2)}, \bar{y}_{(i,3)}) &:= Q(\bar{y}_{(i,0)}, \bar{y}_{(i,1)}, \bar{y}_{(i,2)}, \bar{y}_{(i,3)}) \\
&\} \text{ endfor} \\
&\text{forall } (0 \leq k < 4) \text{ do } \{ \\
(\bar{y}_{(k,0)}, \bar{y}_{(k+1,1)}, \bar{y}_{(k+2,2)}, \bar{y}_{(k+3,3)}) &:= Q(\bar{y}_{(k,0)}, \bar{y}_{(k+1,1)}, \bar{y}_{(k+2,2)}, \bar{y}_{(k+3,3)}) \\
&\} \text{ endfor } \} \text{ endfor} \\
\bar{y}_{(0 \leq i < 4, 0 \leq j < 4)} &:= \bar{y}_{(i,j)} \oplus \bar{x}_{(i,j)}
\end{aligned} \tag{3.3.ii}$$

We can define $\ell = 128$ and $\lambda = 4 = 512$ bits, and therefore let this function of $\bar{\mathbf{x}} \rightarrow \bar{\mathbf{y}}$ be defined as $\hat{\mathbf{y}} = e(\circ, \hat{\mathbf{x}} \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^\lambda)$, where e encrypts lblocks instead of sblocks, making our new notation far easier to understand (and also relating it to CTR in a clearer way) while still indicating it is not like block ciphers, even though it can produce a stream cipher.

The key, nonce, position, and a constant are all packed into this 512 bit block.

The constants are:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{x}_{(0,0)} &:= 61707865h = \text{“expa”} \\ \bar{x}_{(1,0)} &:= 3320646Eh = \text{“nd 3”} \\ \bar{x}_{(2,0)} &:= 79622D32h = \text{“2-by”} \\ \bar{x}_{(3,0)} &:= 6B206574h = \text{“te k”} \end{aligned} \tag{3.3.iii}$$

and together, they write out the first 16 characters of “expand 32-byte key”.

The key is placed in $\bar{x}_{(0,1)} \parallel \bar{x}_{(1,1)} \parallel \bar{x}_{(2,1)} \parallel \bar{x}_{(3,1)} \parallel \bar{x}_{(0,2)} \parallel \bar{x}_{(1,2)} \parallel \bar{x}_{(2,2)} \parallel \bar{x}_{(3,2)}$, meaning it takes up 8 words and is 256-bit / 32-byte.

The stream position and nonce are placed in the last row. The nonce and position could reasonably be counted as a single stream position counter, but RFC 8439 states $\bar{x}_{(0,3)}$ will be stream position, and $\bar{x}_{(1 \leq i < 4, 3)}$ will be a value that does not repeat for the same key.

The key and nonce are selected, and the stream position is incremented for each block, and reset to zero on a nonce change. RFC 5116 also recommends that the upper 64 bits of the nonce field should be a ‘nonce counter’, with the lower 32 bits (a single word in this case) being the pseudorandom nonce itself. Alternatively, for stationary data (mainly disk encryption), the lower 32 bits are recommended to be a common value, the middle 32 bits a differing value but static for a specific sector, and the upper 32 bits only a counter [Mcg08^a].

Poly1305 [NirLan15,2^c] is an authentication algorithm similar to the Galois Message Authentication Code, except it works in $\mathbb{Z}/(2^{130} - 5)$ instead of $\mathbb{GF}(2^{128})$. It takes the message, interprets it as strings of 16 bytes, evaluates them as a polynomial modulo $2^{130} - 5$, and adds a secret pad value to randomise it.

The message is first broken into blocks of 16 bytes in little-endian, with the last block not being 16 bytes long. Each block has the byte $01h$ appended to the end of the last byte in the block, making most blocks 17 bytes or 129 bits, and the final block will be any $8n + 1, n \leq 16$ bits long (since the $01h$ byte will always be at an actual byte index, rather than half in one byte and half in the next). They are then evaluated with Horner’s method of polynomial evaluation mod $2^{130} - 5$ with an x-value (see Section A.2, Item 1)

generated from the first 128-bit secret key, and then reduces it modulo 2^{128} and adds the second 128-bit secret key to it. The first key can be repeated as long as the second key is changed for every authentication, but more often is both keys are changed for a new 256 bit key.

The nature of polynomial evaluation in a finite field is that some x -values will not generate a full-strength tag, the trivial values being $x = 0, 1$. These trivial elements, as well as many other elements that produce a tag of some value, but not a full strength tag, are said to have a multiplicative order of less than $2^{130} - 6$. By definition, any order Ω must satisfy $\Omega | (2^{130} - 6)$, and so the amount of prime factors of $2^{130} - 6$ is very important. It has 4 prime factors, $2^{130} - 6 = 2 \times 23 \times 32985101 \times 897064739519922787230182993783$, and so we can find how many of them are generators, since a generator would be equal to any generator raised to a power that is not zero when reduced modulo any of these prime factors. Since we don't want to know what they are, only how many there are, we do not need a value for that first generator, only the amount of unique powers there are following these rules. This is $(2 - 1) \times (23 - 1) \times (32985101 - 1) \times (897064739519922787230182993783 - 1)$, since in each smaller field, the power can be any value except 0. This means the relative density of generators is

$$\frac{1 \times 22 \times 32985100 \times 897064739519922787230182993782}{2^{130} - 5} = 0.47826085506591753$$

I will ignore any slight skewing that the bit clamping often done applies to this value.

This leads to a table, as shown below, that dictates the amount of elements within $\mathbb{Z}/(2^{130} - 6)$ with each possible order. The tables used show the element 0 as having an order of 1, just like the element of 1. Let P_{30} indicate the 30-digit prime $897064739519922787230182993783$, for space.

order 1 or "0" relative 7.3468×10^{-40}	count 2 density 1.4694×10^{-39}
order 2 relative 1.4694×10^{-39}	count 1 density 7.3468×10^{-40}
order 23 relative 1.6898×10^{-38}	count 22 density 1.6163×10^{-38}
order 46 relative 3.3795×10^{-38}	count 22 density 1.6163×10^{-38}
order 32985101 relative 2.4234×10^{-32}	count 32985100 density 2.4234×10^{-32}
order 65970202 relative 4.8467×10^{-32}	count 32985100 density 2.4234×10^{-32}
order 758657323	count 725672200

relative 5.5737×10^{-31}	density 5.3314×10^{-31}
order 1517314646 relative 1.1147×10^{-30}	count 725672200 density 5.3314×10^{-31}
order P_{30} relative 6.5906×10^{-10}	count $(P_{30} - 1)$ density 6.5906×10^{-10}
order $P_{30} \times 2$ relative 1.3181×10^{-9}	count $(P_{30} - 1)$ density 6.5906×10^{-10}
order $P_{30} \times 23$ relative 1.5158×10^{-8}	count $(P_{30} - 1) \times 22$ density 1.4499×10^{-8}
order $P_{30} \times 46$ relative 3.0317×10^{-8}	count $(P_{30} - 1) \times 22$ density 1.4499×10^{-8}
order $P_{30} \times 32985101$ relative 2.1739×10^{-2}	count $(P_{30} - 1) \times 32985100$ density 2.1739×10^{-2}
order $P_{30} \times 65970202$ relative 4.3478×10^{-2}	count $(P_{30} - 1) \times 32985100$ density 2.1739×10^{-2}
order $P_{30} \times 758657323$ relative 5.0000×10^{-1}	count $(P_{30} - 1) \times 725672200$ density 4.7826×10^{-1}
order $P_{30} \times 1517314646$ relative 1.0000×10^0	count $(P_{30} - 1) \times 725672200$ density 4.7826×10^{-1}

Table 3: $\mathbb{Z}/(2^{130} - 5)$ order table

This gives an average relative order of 0.718809051932076 [Sin26^b] if a random element is selected and its order is calculated. This means Poly1305 falls to a similar attack to that described on GMAC, although requires less plaintexts/verifications, and has a slightly higher chance of succeeding. However, this is assuming the Poly1305 implementation used as an encryption-verification dual does not produce a new $\mathbb{Z}/(2^{130} - 5)$ x-value key for each individual authentication, and only produces a new $\mathbb{Z}/(2^{128})$ constant term key for each individual authentication. If a new x-value is produced as well (meaning a completely new 256-bit key), then this attack fails. According to RFC 8439 [NirLan15,3^d], the full 256-bit key is recommended to be regenerated each time, removing this potential attack from most uses. The Poly1305 key is generated by using the first 256 bits of the first stream cipher block as the key, destroying the last 256 bits of the same block, and encrypting the plaintext with the stream cipher beginning at the next block.

3.4 Counter / Cipher Block Chaining Message Authentication Code Mode

There is no primary field for this section (simply treated as $\mathbb{Z}/(2^\ell) \cong \mathbb{S}$).

Counter / Cipher-Block-Chaining Message-Authentication-Code Mode (CCM) is a two-pass AEAD that uses Counter Mode (CTR) and Cipher-Block-Chaining Message-Authentication-Code Mode (CBCMAC) to give a ciphertext and tag pair. It works by first authenticating the plaintext with CBCMAC, in which an initial nonce value is enciphered to form an initial state, then each state is xored with the next plaintext block and enciphered to form the next state, with the final state being the authentication tag. CTR encryption, where the plaintext is xored with the encipherment of a counter block, i.e. the index of the block, is then carried out on the plaintext and the tag together. This can be represented as

$$\ell = 128$$

$$\lambda = \text{none}$$

$$\tau \leq 128$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{Q}[0] &\leftarrow (\text{bits}_{128} : |\dot{A}|) \\
\hat{Q}[1] &\leftarrow (\text{bits}_{128} : |\dot{P}|) \\
\hat{Q}[2 : 2 + \phi_{128}(\dot{A})] &\leftarrow \pi_{128}(\dot{A}) \\
\hat{Q}[2 + \phi_{128}(\dot{A}) : 2 + \phi_{128}(\dot{A}) + \phi_{128}(\dot{P})] &\leftarrow \pi_{128}(\dot{P}) \\
\hat{R}[0] &:= e(\dot{K}, \hat{I}) \\
\hat{R}[1 \leq i < |\hat{Q}| + 1] &:= e(\dot{K}, \hat{R}[i - 1] \oplus \hat{Q}[i - 1]) \\
\hat{i} &:= e(\dot{K}, \hat{I}) \\
\hat{i}[0 \leq i < 1 + \phi_{128}(\dot{P})] &:= e(\dot{K}, \hat{i} + i) \\
\dot{Y} &:= (\text{bits}_{\tau} : \hat{R}[|\hat{Q}|] \oplus \hat{i}[0]) \\
\dot{C} &:= \dot{P} \oplus (\hat{i}[1 :] \rightarrow \mathbb{b}^*)[0 : |\dot{P}|]
\end{aligned} \tag{3.4.i}$$

(See [Section A.3, Item 1](#)) [Equation 3.4.i](#) shows the authentication of \dot{A} and \dot{P} into $\hat{R}[|\hat{Q}|]$, and then the encryption of \dot{P} and $\hat{R}[|\hat{Q}|]$ into \dot{C} and \dot{Y} .

A Differences Created in Functionalities

A.1 Galois / Counter Mode

1. In most places Galois multiplication is used, as well as the hardware instructions for carryless (unmodulated Galois Field 2) multiplication, a polynomial is formed with bit 0 being the coefficient of x^0 , bit 1 the coefficient of x^1 , and so on until the highest bit [McgVie05,1^b] [Dwo07,1^b]. In the original GCM paper, however, the polynomial is reversed, meaning the least significant bit represents the coefficient of the highest power of x and the most significant bit represents the coefficient of x^0 . In this paper, when describing GCM, I have still used the more common binary polynomial representation, despite it being technically incorrect for the purpose of describing GCM. This keeps general functionalities the same, as well as the mathematical strengths and weaknesses, but changes the exact values that a multiplication or exponentiation results in, meaning the output is different.

A.2 ChaCha20-Poly1305

1. The first secret key is usually clamped to have 22 specific bits set to zero, such as in RFC 8439 [NirLan15,2^e], but that is an optimisation that was made when large integer arithmetic was considerably slower, so the values were made to fit within two double-precision floats, and the tradition has stuck around mostly for backwards compatibility. There is the idea of now unclamping the x-value since large integer arithmetic is much faster, and the extra security by brute force or by potential related-key attacks would be useful considering the current cryptographic landscape of upcoming quantum computers.

A.3 Counter / Cipher Block Chaining Message Authentication Mode

1. The CCM specification allows use of any input sanitisation (called formatting) function and any counter block generation function as long as the formatting function has a first block that is bijective with the nonce (or injective from nonce to block), disallows length extension attacks, and separates \dot{A} and \dot{P} or \dot{C} , and as long as the counter block generation function is based on the full nonce, is based on encipherments of incrementations of some base block does not repeat with a single nonce-key pair, and is unlikely to repeat with different nonce-key pairs.

4 Non-Tweakable Extra Keyed Encryption

4.1 Construction

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{\mathbf{Q}}[0 \leq i < \phi_\ell(\dot{\mathbf{P}})] &\stackrel{e}{\leftarrow} (\text{bits}_{\ell-8} : i) || 00h \oplus XOF_\ell(\dot{\mathbf{I}}) \\
\hat{\mathbf{R}}[0 \leq i < \phi_\ell(\dot{\mathbf{P}})] &\stackrel{e}{\leftarrow} (\text{bits}_{\ell-8} : i) || 01h \oplus XOF_\ell(\dot{\mathbf{I}}) \\
\hat{\mathbf{R}}[0 \leq i < \phi_\ell(\dot{\mathbf{P}})] &:= \bigoplus_{j=0}^{\phi_\ell(\dot{\mathbf{S}})-1} (\hat{\mathbf{R}}[i]^{j+1} \otimes (\pi_\ell(\dot{\mathbf{S}}) \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^*)[j]) \\
\dot{\mathbf{C}}[0 \leq i < |\dot{\mathbf{P}}|] &:= \dot{\mathbf{P}}[i] \oplus (\hat{\mathbf{Q}} \rightarrow \mathbb{b}^*)[i] \oplus (\hat{\mathbf{R}} \rightarrow \mathbb{b}^*)[i] \\
\hat{\xi}[0 \leq i < \phi_\ell(\tau)] &\stackrel{e}{\leftarrow} (\text{bits}_{\ell-8} : i) || 02h \oplus XOF_\ell(\dot{\mathbf{I}}) \\
\hat{\mathbf{V}}_0[0 \leq i < \phi_\ell(\tau)] &\stackrel{e}{\leftarrow} (\text{bits}_{\ell-8} : i) || 80h \oplus XOF_\ell(\dot{\mathbf{I}}) \\
\hat{\mathbf{V}}_1 &\stackrel{e}{\leftarrow} (\text{bits}_{\ell-8} : \tau) || 81h \oplus XOF_\ell(\dot{\mathbf{I}}) \\
\hat{\mathbf{V}}_2 &\stackrel{e}{\leftarrow} (\text{bits}_{\ell-8} : |\dot{\mathbf{S}}|) || 82h \oplus XOF_\ell(\dot{\mathbf{I}}) \\
\hat{\mathbf{V}}_3 &\stackrel{e}{\leftarrow} (\text{bits}_{\ell-8} : |\dot{\mathbf{A}}|) || 83h \oplus XOF_\ell(\dot{\mathbf{I}}) \\
\hat{\mathbf{V}}_4 &\stackrel{e}{\leftarrow} (\text{bits}_{\ell-8} : |\dot{\mathbf{C}}|) || 84h \oplus XOF_\ell(\dot{\mathbf{I}}) \\
\hat{\mathbf{V}}_5[0 \leq i < \phi_\ell(\tau)] &\stackrel{e}{\leftarrow} (\text{bits}_{\ell-8} : i) || 85h \oplus XOF_\ell(\dot{\mathbf{I}}) \\
\hat{\mathbf{U}} &\leftarrow \hat{\mathbf{V}}_1 || \hat{\mathbf{V}}_2 || \pi_\ell(\dot{\mathbf{S}}) || \hat{\mathbf{V}}_3 || \pi_\ell(\dot{\mathbf{A}}) || \hat{\mathbf{V}}_4 || \pi_\ell(\dot{\mathbf{C}}) \\
\hat{\mathbf{Y}}[0 \leq i < \phi_\ell(\tau)] &:= \hat{\mathbf{V}}_0[i] \oplus (\hat{\mathbf{V}}_5[i] \otimes \hat{\xi}[i]^{|\hat{\mathbf{U}}|+1}) \\
\hat{\mathbf{Y}}[0 \leq i < \phi_\ell(\tau)] &:= \hat{\mathbf{Y}}[i] \oplus \bigoplus_{j=0}^{|\hat{\mathbf{U}}|-1} (\hat{\mathbf{U}}[j] \otimes \hat{\xi}[i]^{j+1}) \\
\dot{\mathbf{Y}} &:= (\text{bits}_\tau : \hat{\mathbf{Y}})
\end{aligned} \tag{4.1.i}$$

Equation 4.1.i shows the encryption of $\dot{\mathbf{P}}$ into $\dot{\mathbf{C}}$, as well as the authentication of $\dot{\mathbf{S}}$, $\dot{\mathbf{A}}$, and $\dot{\mathbf{C}}$ into $\dot{\mathbf{Y}}$. All block cipher encipherment calls are domain-separated, in order to remove any potential algebraic weaknesses with polynomial evaluations without shrinking the input-space by too much; and xored with a pseudorandom sblock formed as a digest of $\dot{\mathbf{I}}$, in order to remove any order in $\dot{\mathbf{I}}$ (such as if it were a simple message counter).

The extra keying data, $\dot{\mathbf{S}}$, is evaluated as a polynomial, along with a pseudorandomly generated constant term, $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}[i]$ which is different for each sblock, and the y-value, $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}[i] \oplus \hat{\mathbf{R}}[i]$, is used as the stream cipher sblock for the corresponding plaintext sblock. Since this is a stream cipher like GCM, this allows partial last blocks. Multiple x-values, $\hat{\xi}$, are then generated, and

multiple ℓ -bit tags are produced by constructing a polynomial for each x-value and evaluating it at the given x-value to produce each individual tag. The polynomial used for x-value $\hat{\mathbf{X}}[i]$ is

$$\hat{\mathbf{V}}_0[i] \parallel \hat{\mathbf{V}}_1 \parallel \hat{\mathbf{V}}_2 \parallel \pi_\ell(\hat{\mathbf{S}}) \parallel \hat{\mathbf{V}}_3 \parallel \pi_\ell(\hat{\mathbf{A}}) \parallel \hat{\mathbf{V}}_4 \parallel \pi_\ell(\hat{\mathbf{C}}) \parallel \hat{\mathbf{V}}_5[i]$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{V}}_0[i]$ is the constant term. Each tag is then concatenated into one, and truncated to the exact bit length. Each of $\hat{\mathbf{V}}_1$, $\hat{\mathbf{V}}_2$, $\hat{\mathbf{V}}_3$, and $\hat{\mathbf{V}}_4$ work to make sure that any change in any input (such as producing one less bit of authentication, even if the tag count stays the same) will change the output completely.

4.1.1 Alternative Authentication

This authentication method relies on statistical strength that, after picking many x-values, they will together be at least as strong as the maximum strength, as well as a larger tag (that isn't compressed into a small state before producing the tag) being harder to collide in general. However, there may be a situation in which it must be guaranteed to be the maximum strength it could be at its size: in this scenario, all x-values would need to be multiplicative generators of $\mathbb{GF}(2^\ell)$.

This can be done as shown below, using two (can be public) seeding generators, a two generator state, and one generator output per state permutation. The basic function is a pseudorandom transformation of two generators into another two generators. We name the two generators in the state α_i and β_i , and the outputted generator γ_i . We start with α_0 and β_0 as a public seed pair, then transform α_0 into β_1 and β_0 into γ_1 using this basic function, with $\alpha_1 = \beta_0$. This gives way to a table like this:

$$\begin{array}{llll} \alpha_0 & & \beta_0 & \\ \alpha_1 = \beta_0 & \beta_1 = F(\alpha_0) & \gamma_1 = F(\beta_0) & \\ \alpha_2 = \beta_1 & \beta_2 = F(\alpha_1) & \gamma_2 = F(\beta_1) & \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \end{array} \quad (4.1.1.i)$$

Laying it out like this, we see that α_0 is used to generate β_1 , and β_0 is used to generate α_1 and γ_1 , but only β_1 and γ_1 undergo this basic function F : whenever a value produces a value to the right, it undergoes F ; to the left it is simply copied.

For this basic function, some sampling is required. This is why this method is not a part of the main authentication, as it could lead to timing side-channel attacks, and should only be used where any party who generates

these x-values is not susceptible to timing attacks, or where it is necessary to compress authentication security into less bits.

The basic function is a permutation of (α_0, β_0) into (α_1, β_1) (meaning they have different names to their names in the full generating method). It uses the output values of the block cipher that would normally become the x-values themselves, as well as a hash function for pseudorandom values.

Within a permutation round, \hat{e}_1 and \hat{e}_2 will be two distinct values: how they are generated will be shown later. H is the hash function used. It also makes use of the order function (implicitly, by the definition of $\omega(\alpha^k)$) from the GCM section.

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{n} &:= \hat{e}_1 \\
\hat{m} &:= \hat{e}_2 \\
\hat{n}' &:= H(\hat{\alpha}_0 || \hat{\beta}_0 || \hat{\alpha}_0^{\hat{n}} || \hat{m}) \\
\hat{m}' &:= H(\hat{\beta}_0 || \hat{\alpha}_0 || \hat{\beta}_0^{\hat{m}} || \hat{n}) \\
\hat{k}' &:= \min_{\hat{k}' \geq 0} (\gcd(\hat{n} \times \hat{n}' + \hat{k}', 2^\ell - 1) = 1) \\
\hat{l}' &:= \min_{\hat{l}' \geq 0} (\gcd(\hat{m} \times \hat{m}' + \hat{l}', 2^\ell - 1) = 1) \\
\hat{\alpha}_1 &:= \hat{\alpha}_0^{\hat{n} \times \hat{n}' + \hat{k}'} \\
\hat{\beta}_1 &:= \hat{\beta}_0^{\hat{m} \times \hat{m}' + \hat{l}'}
\end{aligned} \tag{4.1.1.ii}$$

The lines to calculate \hat{k}' and \hat{l}' require sampling, as they cannot be computed in the same time every time.

For the generation of \hat{e}_1 and \hat{e}_2 , an incremental cipher is used, i.e. it enciphers the values 0, 1, 2, etc in some way, but in order to be properly balanced, since \hat{n} and \hat{m} are used as exponents in $\mathbb{GF}(2^\ell)$, which is equivalent to a multiplier in $\mathbb{Z}/(2^\ell - 1)$, and so the value $n = 2^\ell - 1$ or $m = 2^\ell - 1$ would mean that the chance that $\alpha_0^n = 1$ is slightly larger, and so these are removed. Since only one encipherment will give this value, it is sufficient to precompute one extra encipherment, and whenever the value $2^\ell - 1$ is given, simply replace it with this precomputed value. Additionally, the γ values generated are the $\hat{\xi}$ values used in the full encryption and authentication equation.

This gives the new ξ -generation section of the equation:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \hat{\xi}' \stackrel{e}{\leftarrow} (\text{bits}_{\ell-8} : 0) \parallel 02h \oplus XOF_{\ell}(\hat{\mathbf{I}}) \\
\hat{\xi}_0[0 \leq i < \phi_{\ell}(\tau)] & \stackrel{e}{\leftarrow} (\text{bits}_{\ell-8} : 1 + i) \parallel 02h \oplus XOF_{\ell}(\hat{\mathbf{I}}) \\
\hat{\xi}_1[0 \leq i < \phi_{\ell}(\tau)] & \stackrel{e}{\leftarrow} (\text{bits}_{\ell-8} : i - \phi_{\ell}(\tau)) \parallel 02h \oplus XOF_{\ell}(\hat{\mathbf{I}}) \\
& \text{if } (\hat{\xi}_{0 \leq j < 2}[0 \leq i < \phi_{\ell}(\tau)] = (\text{bits}_{\ell} : 2^{\ell} - 1) \rightarrow \mathbb{S}) \\
& \text{then } \{ \hat{\xi}_j[i] := \hat{\xi}' \} \text{ endif} \\
\hat{\alpha}[0] & := \alpha_0 \\
\hat{\beta}[0] & := \beta_0 \\
& \text{forall } (0 \leq i < \phi_{\ell}(\tau)) \text{ do } \{ \\
& \hat{n}'[i] \leftarrow H((\hat{\alpha}[i] \parallel \hat{\beta}[i] \parallel \hat{\alpha}[i]^{\hat{\xi}_0[i]} \parallel \hat{\xi}_1[i]) \rightarrow \mathbb{b}^{\ell}) \quad (4.1.1.iii) \\
& \hat{m}'[i] \leftarrow H((\hat{\beta}[i] \parallel \hat{\alpha}[i] \parallel \hat{\beta}[i]^{\hat{\xi}_1[i]} \parallel \hat{\xi}_0[i]) \rightarrow \mathbb{b}^{\ell}) \\
& \hat{k}'[i] := \min_{\hat{k} \geq 0} (\text{gcd}(\hat{\xi}_0[i] \times \hat{n}'[i] + \hat{k}, 2^{\ell} - 1) = 1) \\
& \hat{l}'[i] := \min_{\hat{l} \geq 0} (\text{gcd}(\hat{\xi}_1[i] \times \hat{m}'[i] + \hat{l}, 2^{\ell} - 1) = 1) \\
& \hat{\alpha}[i + 1] := \hat{\beta}[i] \\
& \hat{\beta}[i + 1] := \hat{\alpha}[i]^{\hat{\xi}_0[i] \times \hat{n}'[i] + \hat{k}'[i]} \\
& \hat{\xi}[i] := \hat{\beta}[i]^{\hat{\xi}_1[i] \times \hat{m}'[i] + \hat{l}'[i]} \\
& \} \text{ endfor}
\end{aligned}$$

4.1.2 Potential Alterations

Again, this is not meant to be a specification, but a template. Because of this, some parts of this construction have been chosen arbitrarily, or as small efficiencies in hardware that can be changed. For example:

- The polynomial evaluations can be done using Horner's method, like GCM, but here has been shown to not use Horner's method, and instead the more 'intuitive' approach.
- I have used one byte (8 bits) for domain separation (despite having only 9 different 'domains'), as this can allow simple insertion into a wide register (such as the `pinsrb` instruction on x86.64 introduced in SSE4.1 for inserting a variable byte into an arbitrary static byte index in a 16 byte (128 bit) register), but any amount of separation can be used, or even none if it is provably as safe (I have not searched for any

specific weaknesses, the separation is more of a safety net, especially as its restriction is negligible).

- The values used in the domain separation are arbitrary, and should have no effect on the output (other than randomising it when changed) as long as they are not duplicated.
- More sections could be added to the authentication polynomial as long as the total length (including all separation sblocks) is not above $2^\ell - 1$ sblocks. (More encryption methods could be added as well, again as long as they provably do not subtract from the strength of the system.)
- A value $\hat{I} \rightarrow \mathbb{b}^\ell$ could be used instead of $XOF_\ell(\hat{I})$ as long as \hat{I} is pseudorandomly generated and will be: neither a message counter, a timestamp, or similar incrementing or predictable value; nor likely to repeat in less than $2^{\ell-1}$ generations. Under these conditions, the XOF need not be used. However, a pseudorandom value (from a co-created pseudorandom value, i.e. no party can poison the compressed nonce value) is generally strong.
- In the alternative authentication method equations, $\hat{\xi}'$, $\hat{\xi}_0$, and $\hat{\xi}_1$ can be generated with any $(\ell - 8)$ -bit values (or $(\ell - k)$ -bit values when changing the domain separation) as long as all inputs to the enciphering function are still guaranteed to be different. I have used $i - \phi_\ell(\tau)$ for $\hat{\xi}_1$ because it fits on the page and follows the previous conditions.

4.2 Security Proofs

4.2.1 Assumptions

- The underlying block cipher is resistant to differential-style attacks, and so has no strong characteristics through the encryption function or across multiple executions of the encryption function.
- A reasonably-sized polynomial's x-values are not likely to be able to be found from coefficients and y-values.
- A reasonably-sized polynomial's coefficients are not likely to be able to be found from a small number of x-value y-value pairs.

4.2.2 Basic Proofs

- 1) Encryption through stream cipher $(\hat{Q} \rightarrow \mathbb{b}^*) \oplus (\hat{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{b}^*)$ is at least as strong as encryption through GCM.

-
- 1.1) If the underlying block cipher is resistant to differential-style attacks, there will be no characteristic between \hat{Q} and \hat{R} when they are first generated by encipherment. Following this point, only non-key-based changes are made to the two values, which means there will still be no characteristic between the two stream ciphers.
 - 1.2) If two completely independent encryption mechanisms are composed into one, the final mechanism will be at least as strong as the stronger of the two individual mechanisms.
 - 1.3) Any two injective sanitisation functions (such as adding a constant term to a counter like in NTEKE \hat{Q} - and \hat{R} -generation, as well as CTR encryption) with the same size domain and range, followed by a block encipherment to generate blocks to be used as a stream cipher, will generate a stream cipher of the same strength as each other.
 - 1.4) Points (1.1, 1.2) show that encryption via stream cipher $(\hat{Q} \rightarrow \mathbb{b}^*) \oplus (\hat{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{b}^*)$ is at least as strong as encryption via stream cipher $\hat{Q} \rightarrow \mathbb{b}^*$, and point (1.3) shows that this is the same strength as CTR encryption.

Therefore, encryption via stream cipher $(\hat{Q} \rightarrow \mathbb{b}^*) \oplus (\hat{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{b}^*)$ is at least as strong as encryption used by GCM.

- 2) Authentication via NTEKE's regular authentication is at least as strong as authentication via GCM.
 - 2.1) By point (1.3), each x-value individually has the same probable strength as the x-value generated for GMAC. This means that each tag individually has the same strength as a full length GMAC tag.
 - 2.2) A string formed by concatenation of multiple polynomial evaluation tags could only be weaker than one individual tag by one method: partial reconstruction of the polynomial. By point (1.3) we know that this too is infeasible, as the x-values are both unpredictable and unrelated.
 - a) This is also infeasible due to the pseudorandom index-based constant term added, as well as the pseudorandom index-based highest power coefficient.
 - 2.3) By point (2.2), a string formed by multiple polynomial evaluation tags must be at least as strong as the strongest of the individual

tags it is composed of. The individual tags are each on average as strong as a random GMAC authentication tag, and so an NTEKE regular tag will be on average at least as strong as a random GMAC authentication tag.

Therefore, authentication via NTEKE's regular authentication is at least as strong as authentication via GCM.

3) Authentication via NTEKE's sampled authentication is at least as strong as authentication via GCM.

3.1) NTEKE's sampled authentication, beyond the xi generation function, will always be at least as strong as NTEKE's regular authentication. Due to this, the only extra attack surface is the (potentially public) generator seeds and the xi generation function.

3.2) Regular xi generation, beyond initialisation vector, key, and extra keying material selection, has $\mathcal{H} = 0$ bits of entropy. Seeds used for sampled xi generation, for all reasonable ℓ (in these calculations, ℓ is assumed to be one of the aforementioned values, where $\ell \in \{2^x : 1 < x \in \mathbb{Z}\}$), have an entropy of $2 \times \ell - 3 \ll \mathcal{H}_\ell \leq 2 \times \ell - 2$ bits (but if $\ell \leq 32$ then entropy is guaranteed to be the largest in that bound with $\mathcal{H}_\ell = 2 \times \ell - 2$). This means that a simple seed change has enough entropy to discard any rainbow tables or similar against a xi generation function, though they are still a risk.

a) This also means that a private seed pair would add a significant amount of entropy to authentication randomisation, and so constant message count generator negotiation algorithms could be useful if this is used in a symmetric transmission protocol. Alternatively, a public seed can be used, the first two outputs discarded, the next two outputs used as a seed for the first message's authentication, then the second message's authentication, and continued.

§ See [Section B.1](#) for more information on seed-pair entropy.

3.3) The xi values are generated as: (potentially public previous generator) to the power of [(pseudorandom cipher output) times (pseudorandom hash output) plus (low sampled integer)]. Excluding the sampled integer, it will produce a pseudorandom value excepting the value consisting of all zero bits. Adding the sampled

integer essentially rounds the power up so it makes the next lowest generator element. This will group certain products together, as they will be moved to the same generator, but if the entropy is large enough, it will still consist of enough options for the seed state to be useless in determining the current state. For example, if the first two output xi values generated are discarded, then both state generators will be morphed based on the key, and since the current state can only be guessed at with slightly higher than random accuracy, the next morph will be considerably more secure, as an attacker does not know which elements would be grouped together, as the base of the exponentiation is unknown.

- 3.4) From point (3.3), we know that the output of the sampled xi generation function is pseudorandom and based on the key and nonce. From point (1.3), we know that this is therefore comparable to the regular xi generation function.

Therefore, authentication via NTEKE's sampled authentication is at least as secure as authentication via GCM.

4.2.3 Proper Proofs

- 1) Encryption via stream cipher $(\hat{Q} \rightarrow \mathbb{b}^*) \oplus (\hat{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{b}^*)$ has $\min(|\hat{C}|, |\hat{K}| + \ell + |\hat{S}|)$ bits of security against distinguishing chosen plaintext attacks.
 - 1.1) Since $(2^\ell)!$ (the total amount of possible permutations of sblocks) is much larger than $2^{|\hat{K}|}$ (the amount of permutations \hat{K} can represent), it is overwhelmingly unlikely that $e(\hat{K}, \hat{M} \oplus \hat{I})$ is equal to $e(\hat{K}', \hat{M})$ for constant \hat{K} , \hat{K}' and \hat{I} and a non-negligible amount of $\hat{M} \in \mathcal{S}$. This means \hat{K} and $XOF_\ell(\hat{I})$ each contribute $|\hat{K}|$ bits and ℓ bits, respectively, to the amount of entropy when using the block cipher as a primitive function in NTEKE (generation of \hat{Q} , generation of \hat{V}_0 , etc).
 - 1.2) n bits of evaluations of an m -bit value as a polynomial will contain $\min(n, m)$ bits of entropy.
 - 1.2.1) Given all coefficients of a polynomial, any x-value y-value pair can be generated with an x-value within the field in use.
 - 1.2.2) Given k x-value y-value pairs with distinct x-values, a $k - 1$ degree polynomial fitting all given points can be formed, in turn allowing generation of more points on this polynomial (which is implied to be the original polynomial).

- 1.2.3) n bits of data has a trivial upper limit of n bits of entropy.
- 1.2.4) m coefficients generating $n \geq m$ points uniquely identifies the coefficients by point (1.2.2), and therefore there is another upper limit on entropy, the total upper limit of the coefficients' entropy.
- 1.2.5) For partial final coefficients or evaluations, we can say r bits are missing from the end of the final coefficient / evaluation (which are assumed to be $(bits_r : 0)$, i.e. the coefficients / evaluations undergo π_η). This means there are 2^r options for the solutions of these r bits when we are inverting the relation, whether we are calculating evaluations from coefficients or coefficients from evaluations. Since this is symmetrical, there is an average of one solution per input to this relation, regardless of r or direction of transformation, and so, on average, the sub-statement is correct.

Therefore, n bits of evaluations of an m -bit value as a polynomial will contain $\min(m, n)$ bits of entropy.

- 1.3) The stream cipher $\hat{\mathbf{Q}} \rightarrow \mathbb{b}^*$ is a pseudorandom permutation of block index to sblock value. The stream cipher $\hat{\mathbf{R}} \rightarrow \mathbb{b}^*$ is a polynomial evaluation of $\pi_\ell(\hat{\mathbf{S}}) \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^*$. If we combine them through the xor function, we have a sequence of sblocks that acts as a pseudorandom function regardless of output length, i.e. it can now produce repetitions of blocks whilst being secure. If we follow the entropy through the encryption function, we see that the entropy of the stream cipher is $\min(|\hat{\mathbf{P}}|, |\hat{\mathbf{K}}| + \ell + |\hat{\mathbf{S}}|)$.
- 1.4) Entropy given in point (1.3) translates directly into stream cipher strength against CPA if all components $(\hat{\mathbf{K}}, XOF_\ell(\hat{\mathbf{I}}), \hat{\mathbf{S}})$ are unpredictable.

Therefore, stream cipher $(\hat{\mathbf{Q}} \rightarrow \mathbb{b}^*) \oplus (\hat{\mathbf{R}} \rightarrow \mathbb{b}^*)$ has $\min(|\hat{\mathbf{C}}|, |\hat{\mathbf{K}}| + \ell + |\hat{\mathbf{S}}|)$ bits of security in an IND-CPA scheme.

- 2) Authentication by regular xi generation has up to τ bits of strongly unforgeable security against chosen message attacks.
- 2.1) We can interpret $\hat{\mathbf{V}}_0$ and $\hat{\xi}^k \otimes \hat{\mathbf{V}}_5$ as simple stream ciphers, and the evaluation of $\hat{\mathbf{U}}$ as the evaluation of a secret polynomial, since it contains a secret portion. This allows us to apply point (1.3), and find that the entropy of $\hat{\mathbf{Y}}$ is $\min(\tau, |\hat{\mathbf{K}}| + \min(|\hat{\mathbf{K}}|, 7 \times \ell) + |\hat{\mathbf{S}}|)$. (Note that one ℓ comes from the nonce, and the other six come

from $\hat{V}_{0,5}$ and $\hat{V}_{1,2,3,4}$. If $|\dot{\mathbf{K}}| = n \times \ell$, then n chosen plaintexts will often give a single solution for $\dot{\mathbf{K}}$, and more plaintexts increase the chance of a single solution exponentially. Also note that τ (the length of the authentication tag produced) is also (roughly) the total length of all xi values generated for polynomial evaluation at the authentication step, and so xi value count does not play a meaningful role.)

- 2.2) If all keying data is intractable and unpredictable to a third party, then the entropy of point (2.1) translates directly into strength, and this strength is the bits required to predict any internal part of secret data ($\dot{\mathbf{K}}$, \hat{U} , etc).
- 2.3) Since there is only one tag for any set of key, nonce, and polynomial, existential unforgeability implies strong unforgeability.

Therefore, authentication by regular xi generation has τ bits of security (assuming max general multiplicative order)

- 3) Authentication via sampled xi generation is at least as strong as authentication via regular xi generation. Follow [Section 4.2.2's Point 3](#).
- 4) NTEKE ciphertexts are indistinguishable if an adversary is given a handled encryption oracle (it returns a handle to a hidden random nonce), a specific encryption oracle (it takes a nonce to encrypt with by value), a specific decryption oracle (it takes a nonce to decrypt with by value), and a handled verification oracle (it takes a handle to a hidden random nonce to verify with).
 - 4.1) Assume the two challenge plaintexts are submitted, and one of them is randomly selected to be encrypted with the handled encryption oracle, returning: a handle to the nonce used; the ciphertext for that plaintext and nonce; and the tag for that ciphertext and nonce.
 - 4.2) The attack described in [Section 3.2](#) is not useful if 4 or more tags are produced, as the amount of selections of x-values that give $\Omega < 2^\ell - 1$ becomes incredibly low relative to the total xi value space. (It is also completely useless against sampled xi generation.)
 - 4.3) The specific decryption oracle is useless to the attacker as: it will be guaranteed to work only on the output of the specific encryption oracle, which is a useless combination as the previous attack is not possible against NTEKE; and tags are strongly unforgeable

by points (2, 3), which makes it useless against arbitrary message verification / decryption.

- 4.4) The handled verification oracle is useless to the attacker for the same reasons as point (4.3), and the only extra functionality it has is verifying the ciphertext returns from the scheme after submitting the two challenge plaintexts, which are assumed to be correct anyway.
- 4.5) By points (4.3, 4.4), this environment is reduced to chosen plaintext attacks with a specific encryption oracle (since a specific encryption oracle can emulate a handled encryption oracle if there is anyway no decryption oracle), which NTEKE is secure in by point (1).

Therefore, NTEKE, with either xi generation system, is strong against distinguishing attacks of this environment, which is in turn a stronger assumption than the adaptive chosen ciphertext environment, and so NTEKE is also IND-CCA2 strong.

B NTEKE Extra Information

B.1 Seed-Pair Entropy

For a bit-length ℓ (which is used as the general security factor), define $\psi(\ell)$ as the collection of all primes $p|(2^\ell - 1)$. (Here we assume $2^\ell - 1$ is squarefree, i.e. there is no $q > 1$ such that $(q^2)|(2^\ell - 1)$. Looking at the factorisation of numbers of the form $2^{(2^n)} - 1$ into coprime Fermat numbers, and the fact that all reasonable Fermat numbers are squarefree, we can say this is true for reasonable ℓ .) We define the entropy of a generator of $\mathbb{GF}(2^\ell)$ as $\mathcal{H}_\ell = \sum_{n \in \psi(\ell)} (\log_2(n - 1))$ bits. We define a ratio $\mathcal{R}_\ell = \lceil \ell \div \mathcal{H}_\ell \rceil$, which is used as $\mathcal{H}_\ell \times \mathcal{R}_\ell \geq \ell$, and so if we have \mathcal{R}_ℓ generator elements of $\mathbb{GF}(2^\ell)$, there are at least as many options (at least as much entropy) as selecting one general element of $\mathbb{GF}(2^\ell)$. For all reasonable ℓ , this results in $\mathcal{R}_\ell = 2$, and so it suffices to use 2 instead of calculating this, as long as (astonishingly lax) restrictions are placed on ℓ . This applies to the sampled xi generation; above, I have used a state of two generators, since \mathcal{R}_ℓ is practically guaranteed to be below or equal to 2, but if it were higher in theory, more generators would be required in the xi generation state.

5 Tweakable Di-Key Extra Keyed Encryption

Tweakable Di-Key Extra Keyed Encryption (T2EKE) is a form of Tweakable n-Key Extra Keyed Encryption (TnEKE) that uses two keys ($\dot{\mathbf{K}}_T, \dot{\mathbf{K}}_E$) for tweakable security. This is also the main form of TnEKE.

5.1 Construction

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{\mathbf{T}}[0 \leq i < \lambda] & \stackrel{e, \dot{\mathbf{K}}_T}{\leftarrow} (\text{bits}_{\lambda_i} : i) || \text{XOF}_{\ell-\lambda_i}(00b || \dot{\mathbf{T}} || \dot{\mathbf{I}}) \\
\hat{\mathbf{C}}[0 \leq i < \lambda] & := (\hat{\mathbf{P}}[i] \oplus \hat{\mathbf{T}}[i])^{-1} \\
\hat{\mathbf{Q}}[0 \leq i < \lambda] & \stackrel{e, \dot{\mathbf{K}}_E}{\leftarrow} (\text{bits}_{\lambda_i} : i) || \text{XOF}_{\ell-\lambda_i}(01b || \dot{\mathbf{T}} || \dot{\mathbf{I}}) \\
\hat{\mathbf{D}}[0 \leq i < \lambda] & := \bigoplus_{j=0}^{\lambda-1} (\hat{\mathbf{C}}[j] \otimes \hat{\mathbf{Q}}[i]^j) \\
\hat{\mathbf{C}}[0 \leq i < \lambda] & := (\hat{\mathbf{D}}[i]^{-1} \oplus \hat{\mathbf{T}}[i])^{-1} \\
\hat{\mathbf{D}}[0] & := \hat{\mathbf{C}}[0] \oplus e(\dot{\mathbf{K}}_E, \hat{\mathbf{T}}[0] \oplus (\text{XOF}_{\ell}(\dot{\mathbf{I}} || 00b) \rightarrow \mathbb{S})) \\
\hat{\mathbf{D}}[1 \leq i < \lambda] & := \hat{\mathbf{C}}[i] \oplus e(\dot{\mathbf{K}}_E, \hat{\mathbf{T}}[i] \oplus (\text{XOF}_{\ell}(\dot{\mathbf{I}} || 01b) \rightarrow \mathbb{S}) \oplus \hat{\mathbf{C}}[i-1]) \\
\hat{\mathbf{C}}[0 \leq i < \lambda] & := (\hat{\mathbf{D}}[i]^{-1} \oplus \hat{\mathbf{T}}[i])^{-1} \\
\hat{\mathbf{D}}[0 \leq i < \lambda-1] & := \hat{\mathbf{C}}[i] \oplus e(\dot{\mathbf{K}}_E, \hat{\mathbf{T}}[i] \oplus (\text{XOF}_{\ell}(\dot{\mathbf{I}} || 11b) \rightarrow \mathbb{S}) \oplus \hat{\mathbf{C}}[i+1]) \\
\hat{\mathbf{D}}[\lambda-1] & := \hat{\mathbf{C}}[\lambda-1] \oplus e(\dot{\mathbf{K}}_E, \hat{\mathbf{T}}[\lambda-1] \oplus (\text{XOF}_{\ell}(\dot{\mathbf{I}} || 10b) \rightarrow \mathbb{S})) \\
\hat{\mathbf{C}}[0 \leq i < \lambda] & := \hat{\mathbf{D}}^{-1} \oplus \hat{\mathbf{T}}[i]
\end{aligned} \tag{5.1.i}$$

5.2 Security Proofs

5.2.1 Cryptanalysis

1. The basic tweak insertion function is a function based on the Galois multiplicative inverse and Galois addition operations:

$$\hat{\mathbf{C}} := (\hat{\mathbf{P}}^{-1} \oplus \hat{\mathbf{T}})^{-1} \tag{5.2.1.i}$$

Applying linear cryptanalysis to this function (assuming tweak is not 0) in $\mathbb{GF}(2^8)$, we have a 1/64 chance (exactly 4 per selected tweak or per selected plaintext) that the following equations are true (they are identical):

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{T} \otimes \hat{\delta} &= 1 \\
\hat{T} \otimes (\hat{P} \oplus (\hat{P}^{-1} \oplus \hat{T})^{-1}) &= 1 \\
(\hat{T}^{-1} \otimes \hat{P}^{-1} \oplus 1)^{-1} &= \hat{T} \otimes \hat{P} \oplus 1
\end{aligned} \tag{5.2.1.ii}$$

Additionally, all other deltas have either a 0/256 chance or a 2/256 chance to be fulfilled with a single selected tweak and a random plaintext. This creates the idea that solutions to find \hat{P} from \hat{T} and $\hat{P} \oplus (\hat{P}^{-1} \oplus \hat{T})^{-1}$ come in pairs (such as with the zero plaintext always being one solution for the 1/64 characteristic). To find the \hat{P} solutions from these two values,

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{P} &= \hat{\delta} \otimes \hat{x} \\
\hat{\delta} &= \hat{P} \oplus (\hat{P}^{-1} \oplus \hat{T})^{-1} \\
\hat{P} \oplus \hat{\delta} &= (\hat{P}^{-1} \oplus \hat{T})^{-1} \\
\hat{P} \oplus \hat{\delta} &= (\hat{P}^{-1})^{-1} \otimes (1 \oplus \hat{P} \otimes \hat{T})^{-1} \\
\hat{P}^{-1} \otimes \hat{\delta} &= 1 \oplus (1 \oplus \hat{P} \otimes \hat{T})^{-1} \\
\hat{P}^{-1} \otimes \hat{\delta} &= (1 \oplus \hat{P} \otimes \hat{T} \oplus 1) \otimes (1 \oplus \hat{P} \otimes \hat{T})^{-1} \\
\hat{\delta} &= \hat{P}^2 \otimes \hat{T} \otimes (1 \oplus \hat{P} \otimes \hat{T})^{-1} \\
(1 \oplus \hat{P} \otimes \hat{T}) \otimes \hat{\delta} &= \hat{P}^2 \otimes \hat{T} \\
0 &= \hat{T} \otimes \hat{P}^2 \oplus \hat{\delta} \otimes \hat{T} \otimes \hat{P} \oplus \hat{\delta} \\
0 &= \hat{P}^2 \oplus \hat{\delta} \otimes \hat{P} \oplus \hat{\delta} \otimes \hat{T}^{-1} \\
0 &= \delta^2 \otimes \hat{x}^2 \oplus \hat{\delta}^2 \otimes \hat{x} \oplus \hat{\delta} \otimes \hat{T}^{-1} \\
\hat{\delta}^{-1} \otimes \hat{T}^{-1} &= \hat{x}^2 \oplus \hat{x}
\end{aligned} \tag{5.2.1.iii}$$

This is a reduced quadratic in $\mathbb{GF}(2^\ell)$, and so this gives directly the idea of the paired solutions, though does not yet fully explain the single quad-solution.

Since, in \mathbb{Z}_2 , $(a \oplus b)^2 \oplus (a \oplus b) = (a^2 \oplus a) \oplus (b^2 \oplus b)$, each input bit linearly affects each output bit, and so, in $\mathbb{GF}(2^\ell)$ the function $f(\hat{x}) = \hat{x}^2 \oplus \hat{x}$ can be represented as $f(\hat{x}) = \hat{x} \odot \hat{P}$, where \hat{P} is a binary matrix created simply to be used as a representation of this function, and it should be non-invertible (due to the 2- and 0-solution preimages). Applying the function to the two options of the basis 1, we get $0^2 \oplus 0 = 1^2 \oplus 1 = 0$,

and due to the above $f(a \oplus b) = f(a) \oplus f(b)$ identity, the lowest bit of the input does not affect the output. This can be shown by the lowest row of the given matrix being all 0's (and the matrix therefore being non-invertible).

Using the polynomial defined for $\mathbb{GF}(2^8)$, $x^8 \oplus x^4 \oplus x^3 \oplus x \oplus 1$, I can show an example of this matrix used. The matrix below is simply formed by having each row (the coefficient of each basis component) set to $((x^{2^i} \oplus x^i) \bmod (x^8 \oplus x^4 \oplus x^3 \oplus x \oplus 1)) \rightarrow \mathbb{V}(2^\ell)$, which for $i = 0$ (the bottom row) is $1 \oplus 1 = 0$.

$$(\hat{x}^2 \oplus \hat{x}) \rightarrow \mathbb{V}(2^\ell) = (\hat{x} \rightarrow \mathbb{V}(2^\ell)) \odot \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.2.1.iv)$$

This presents a small problem, as this matrix being invertible would be very useful to find a pre-image of this function, but with a determinant of 0, it is non-invertible; however, this difficulty is to be expected with pre-imaging an injective function. The exact relationship between the two roots can be found easily, with

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{x}^2 \oplus \hat{x} &= \hat{\delta}^{-1} \otimes \hat{T}^{-1} \\ \hat{x} \otimes (\hat{x} \oplus 1) &= \delta^{-1} \otimes \hat{T}^{-1} \end{aligned} \quad (5.2.1.v)$$

which was really trivial, since the lowest bit is the only redundant bit in the input vector.

The equation $\hat{x}^2 \oplus \hat{x} \oplus \hat{\delta}^{-1} \otimes \hat{T}^{-1} = 0$ can be reconstructed as

$$(\hat{x} \rightarrow \mathbb{V}_H(2^\ell)) \odot \begin{array}{c|cccccccc}
0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\
1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\
0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\
0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\
0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
\hline
& & & & & & & & & \hat{\delta}^{-1} \otimes \hat{T}^{-1} \\
& & & & & & & & & 1
\end{array} = \begin{array}{c}
0 \\
0 \\
0 \\
0 \\
0 \\
0 \\
0 \\
0 \\
0 \\
1
\end{array}^\top = (0 \in \mathbb{V}_H(2^\ell)) \tag{5.2.1.vi}$$

with dividing lines for the original 8x8 matrix above.

This gives a set of linear equations that all equate to zero when the value of $\hat{\delta}^{-1} \otimes \hat{T}^{-1}$ is filled in the matrix. Since when casting to $\mathbb{V}_H(2^\ell)$ the ninth value is selected as 1, this is a set of eight equations and seven variables. This gives both the values that have no pre-images and the values that have two pre-images.

For an arbitrary $(\hat{\delta}^{-1} \otimes \hat{T}^{-1})$, this can be solved very quickly, especially for a simple $\ell \leq 1024$, and so \hat{x} 's value pairs are almost always known from the linear differential and the tweak. Therefore, we can find a candidate plaintext, as $\hat{P} = \hat{\delta} \otimes \hat{x}$, and a paired candidate plaintext, $\hat{P} = \hat{\delta} \otimes \hat{x} \oplus \hat{\delta}$.

The quadruple solution comes from $\hat{T} \otimes \hat{\delta} = 1$ and so the two trivial values, $\hat{P} \in \{0, \hat{T}^{-1}\}$, are added. For example, with $\hat{T} = (\text{bits}_8 : 1)$ and $\hat{\delta} = \hat{T}^{-1} = (\text{bits}_8 : 1)$, we have

$$\begin{array}{ll}
\hat{P} = 0 & \text{trivial} \\
\hat{P} = 1 & \because \hat{T}^{-1} = 1 \\
\hat{P} = x^7 \oplus x^5 \oplus x^4 \oplus x^3 \oplus x^2 & \because \hat{x} = x^7 \oplus x^5 \oplus x^4 \oplus x^3 \oplus x^2 \\
\hat{P} = x^7 \oplus x^5 \oplus x^4 \oplus x^3 \oplus x^2 \oplus 1 & \because \hat{x} = x^7 \oplus x^5 \oplus x^4 \oplus x^3 \oplus x^2 \oplus 1
\end{array} \tag{5.2.1.vii}$$

Note that for any tweak with a given modulus polynomial, the same two non-trivial values will contribute to the quadruple-probability characteristic, as well as the 0 plaintext always contributing. The only plaintext contributor to the quadruple-probability characteristic that changes with the tweak is $\hat{P} = \hat{T}^{-1}$.

The reason this gives an “unmathematical” result (four solutions for a quadratic, and an incorrect rightmost value in the produced vector in [Equation 5.2.1.vi](#)) is that I have defined $0^{-1} = 0$ in order to not throw an error “randomly” and potentially leak information.

This means the largest linear characteristic through the basic tweak insertion function, by random plaintext or by random tweak, is $4 * 2^{-\ell} = 2^{2-\ell}$. The worst characteristic is likely the impossible characteristic for one more than half of the potential characteristics, where $\hat{x}^2 \oplus \hat{x} = \hat{\delta}^{-1} \otimes \hat{T}^{-1}$ has no preimages for \hat{x} .

- Applying differential cryptanalysis to the basic tweak insertion function across two plaintexts with a constant tweak gives us these equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\Delta} &= \hat{P}_1 \oplus \hat{P}_2 \\ \hat{C}_i &= (\hat{P}_i^{-1} \oplus \hat{T})^{-1} \\ \hat{\nabla} &= \hat{C}_1 \oplus \hat{C}_2 \end{aligned} \tag{5.2.1.viii}$$

Adding the intermediate differentials, between the ending inversion and the opening inversion, yields the following diagram.

This can be linked to point (1), as shown by the purple symbols below (purple values imply a relation to the named value from point (1), not the values from this point).

Extending this to the last set of boxes:

From this, we can use

$$\hat{P}_i^{-1} = \hat{C}_i^{-1} \oplus \hat{T}$$

$$\hat{P}_1^{-1} \oplus \hat{P}_2^{-1} = (\hat{P}_1 \oplus \hat{P}_2) \otimes (\hat{P}_1 \otimes \hat{P}_2)^{-1}$$

$$\hat{\delta} = \hat{\Delta} \otimes \hat{P}_1^{-1} \otimes \hat{P}_2^{-1}$$

$$\hat{\delta} = \hat{\nabla} \otimes \hat{C}_1^{-1} \otimes \hat{C}_2^{-1}$$

$$\hat{\Delta} \otimes \hat{P}_1^{-1} \otimes \hat{P}_2^{-1} = \hat{\nabla} \otimes (\hat{P}_1^{-1} \oplus \hat{T}) \otimes (\hat{P}_2^{-1} \oplus \hat{T})$$

$$\hat{\Delta} \otimes \hat{P}_1^{-1} \otimes \hat{P}_2^{-1} = \hat{\nabla} \otimes (\hat{P}_1^{-1} \otimes \hat{P}_2^{-1} \oplus (\hat{P}_1^{-1} \oplus \hat{P}_2^{-1}) \otimes \hat{T} \oplus \hat{T}^2)$$

$$(\hat{\Delta} \oplus \hat{\nabla}) \otimes \hat{P}_1^{-1} \otimes \hat{P}_2^{-1} = \hat{\nabla} \otimes \hat{T}^2 \oplus \hat{\nabla} \otimes (\hat{P}_1^{-1} \oplus \hat{P}_2^{-1}) \otimes \hat{T}$$

(5.2.1.ix)

to get another reduced quadratic, and an example of its homogenous vector extension form of $\text{GF}(2^\ell)$,

$$\hat{T} = (\hat{P}_1^{-1} \oplus \hat{P}_2^{-1}) \otimes \hat{x}$$

$$\hat{x} = \hat{T} \otimes (\hat{P}_1^{-1} \oplus \hat{P}_2^{-1})^{-1}$$

$$(\hat{\Delta} \oplus \hat{\nabla}) \otimes \hat{P}_1^{-1} \otimes \hat{P}_2^{-1} = \hat{\nabla} \otimes \hat{T}^2 \oplus \hat{\nabla} \otimes (\hat{P}_1^{-1} \oplus \hat{P}_2^{-1}) \otimes \hat{T}$$

$$(\hat{\Delta} \oplus \hat{\nabla}) \otimes \hat{P}_1^{-1} \otimes \hat{P}_2^{-1} = \hat{\nabla} \otimes \hat{\delta}^2 \otimes \hat{x}^2 \oplus \hat{\nabla} \otimes \hat{\delta}^2 \otimes \hat{x}$$

$$\hat{x}^2 \oplus \hat{x} = (\hat{\Delta} \otimes \hat{\nabla}^{-1} \oplus 1) \otimes \hat{\delta}^{-2} \otimes \hat{P}_1^{-1} \otimes \hat{P}_2^{-1}$$

(5.2.1.x)

$$(\hat{T} \otimes \hat{\delta}^{-1} \rightarrow \mathbb{V}_H(2^\ell)) \odot \left[\begin{array}{cccccccc|c} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \hline (\hat{\Delta} \otimes \hat{\nabla}^{-1} \oplus 1) \otimes \hat{\delta}^{-2} & & & & & & & & 1 \\ \otimes \hat{P}_1^{-1} \otimes \hat{P}_2^{-1} & & & & & & & & \end{array} \right] = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}^\top \quad (5.2.1.xi)$$

This gives a similar conclusion as the previous point of cryptanalysis.

3. If we select two plaintexts, and encrypt each one through: the basic tweak insertion function; a pseudorandom keystream that is different per tweak (but not dependent on other plaintexts or ciphertexts); and then the basic tweak insertion function again – with each plaintext being encrypted by each of two tweaks – we get the following diagram.

We can see the changes in differentials as the quad travels through the various forms of this reduced encryption function by casting it into 3d. Let $\hat{\alpha}$ be $\hat{T}_1 \oplus \hat{T}_2$, and $\hat{\beta}$ be $\hat{K}_1 \oplus \hat{K}_2$.

6 References

[McgVie05]	a	<p>“The Galois/Counter Mode of Operation (GCM)”</p> <p>David A. McGrew & John Viega</p> <p>May 2005</p> <p>[pdf file] : csrc.nist.rip</p>
[McgVie05,1]	b	<p>“The Field $GF(2^{128})$”</p> <p>Section 3, Page 8-10, PDF Page 10-12</p>
[Dwo07]	a	<p>“Recommendation for Block Cipher Modes of Operation: Galois/Counter Mode (GCM) and GMAC”</p> <p>a.k.a. “NIST SP 800-38D”</p> <p>Morris J. Dworkin</p> <p>November 2007</p> <p>[web page] : csrc.nist.gov</p> <p>[pdf file] : doi.org</p>
[Dwo07,1]	b	<p>“Multiplication Operation on Blocks”</p> <p>Section 6.3, Page 11-12, PDF Page 19-20</p>
[Mcg08]		<p>“An Interface and Algorithms for Authenticated Encryption”</p> <p>a.k.a. “IETF RFC 5116”</p> <p>David A. McGrew</p> <p>January 2008</p> <p>[paged html file] : datatracker.ietf.org</p>
[Mcg08,1]	a	<p>“Recommended Nonce Formation”</p> <p>Section 3.2, Page 9-10</p>
[NirLan15]	a	<p>“ChaCha20 and Poly1305 for IETF Protocols”</p> <p>a.k.a. “IETF RFC 8439”</p> <p>Yoav Nir & Adam Langley</p> <p>May 2015</p> <p>[paged html file] : datatracker.ietf.org</p>
[NirLan15,1]	b	<p>“The ChaCha20 Block Function”</p> <p>Section 2.3, Page 7-11</p>

[NirLan15,2]	c e	“The Poly1305 Algorithm” Section 2.5, Page 14-18
[NirLan15,3]	d	“Generating the Poly1305 Key Using ChaCha20” Section 2.6, Page 18-19
[Sin26]	a b	“Field Decompositions” Ishan Singh April 2026 (May 2026 as of v 0.2) [web page] : doi.org

Y Publications

Version 0.2(a)

Full resources available from [zenodo 19742101](https://zenodo.org/record/19742101)

Files listed and supplied as v 0.2

Y.1 Auxiliary Files

/Codes.zip	MD5	0ea62bd8e5dd6f542eb13144 3f6528d9
	SHA2-256	d32b66ec0c007dabb47bf50c 79f333485ae3d4cc991586b2 56309592f1ffab6c
	SHA3-256	d483490ed054dd33138847d2 69c97b2010bb32ea33bfc993 3076da0a122fc590
/FieldDecompositions.pdf	MD5	ffd6c8aa40f5d56ee2f99c2c 2200d7c1
	SHA2-256	dde091bfc4d65b8fe72b73d8 af9cb95040384e4ed9dfa467 a23571cdd7a40a47
	SHA3-256	5816ba09ea8294f4b504a265 9f33d4be98bc7fd94dd60591 79f52ab71cad9091
/FieldDecompositions.zip	MD5	d868cf7db0567f8027887448 47eb0143
	SHA2-256	e9f237f56b5fff959a2edd09 deded8adaedc97867e3171c1 990f2220489f4bd8
	SHA3-256	b802f033ed314e91a603a779 941c1e4f3529059970568fd4 a5e2c07388783b06

Z Changelog

- v 0.1 from v 0.0:
 - Added Section 3.3 “ChaCha20-Poly1305”
 - Added Section A.2 “ChaCha20-Poly1305”
 - Reworded definitions to support $\mathbb{Z}/(2^{130} - 5)$, not just $\mathbb{GF}(2^\ell)$
 - Changed hexadecimal literal format from `0x12AB` to `12ABh`
 - Changed binary literal format from `0b0110` to `0110b`
- v 0.2 from v 0.1:
 - Clarified Poly1305’s keygen method in ChaCha20-Poly1305
 - Fixed an internal link’s colouring in ChaCha20-Poly1305
 - Added missing rows in Table 3 in ChaCha20-Poly1305
 - Added Section 3.4 “Counter / Cipher Block Chaining Message Authentication Code Mode” (incomplete)
 - Compressed NTEKE constants into single byte constants for space and readability
 - Fixed incorrect hexadecimal format constants present in Section 4.1.1 NTEKE Alternative Authentication
 - Ceiling Corrections, for entropy calculations in Section 4.2.3
 - Added Section 5 “Tweakable Di-Key Extra Keyed Encryption” (incomplete)
 - Added definition for tweaks
 - Fixed incorrect zero-handling in `./decomposition.py`
 - Fixed incorrect values in `./FieldDecompositions.pdf`
 - Moved `./decomposition.py` to `./Codes.zip/decomposition.py`
 - Added `./Codes.zip/decomposition.cpp`
 - Added `./Codes.zip/LICENSE-gmp-gmpxx.txt`
 - Fixed the linking to this paper’s resources to auto-resolve to the newest version online
 - v 0.2a: Moved definition of n to before definition of $\omega(\cdot)$
 - v 0.2a: Changed filepath layout to absolute from folder, not including within this list before this location, and not including auxiliary files
 - v 0.2a: Various typographical fixes